

Prioritisation analysis based on blue carbon scores

Deliverable 5.4

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The report represents the most up to date status of the information. Any potential upcoming information may be considered for incorporation in future deliverables to improve the scientific knowledge.

The MPA Europe project

MPA Europe is a project co-funded by the European Union (EU) that will map a network of locations representative of biodiversity in European seas (Atlantic Exclusive Economic Zones of the EU and its neighbours, and all the Mediterranean, Baltic, and Black seas) (Figure A).

Figure A. MPA Europe study area.

This network will indicate where to prioritise placement of Marine Protected Areas (MPA) for biodiversity protection and how Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) can maximise blue carbon benefits. By using a holistic set of biodiversity measures, from species to ecosystems (including habitats), and environmental data including carbon storage, water currents, and climate change velocity models, it will be possible to quantify and map both the present and future connectivity within the proposed MPA network. The multiple scenarios provided will support wider and improved MSP by policy makers, industry, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). The major scientific areas of the project and its outcomes are summarized in the infographic presented in Figure Figure B.

Figure B. MPA Europe project scientific areas

The inter-disciplinary approach of MPA Europe is supported by a diversity of partners. These include Nord University (Norway), the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (Belgium), Aarhus University (Denmark), Climazul (Greece), the Centre of Marine Sciences (Portugal), Science Crunchers (Portugal), the Joint Nature Conservation Committee (England, UK), the Scottish Association for Marine Science (Scotland, UK), the Ocean University of China (China), and the University of the Ryukyus (Japan). The partners include experts in marine biology, taxonomy, ecology, oceanography, biogeochemistry, and biogeography, MPA network design, benthic habitat mapping, carbon dynamics, species distribution, climate modelling, and MSP compose the MPA Europe team.

Deliverable 5.4 overview

This report presents a prioritisation of where marine sediment organic carbon (OC) storage capacity is greatest in the MPA Europe project study area. It uses maps of the modelled OC storage capacity in European seas based on the OC content of upper sediment layers, environmental predictors and an OC content 3-level score developed under the project WP4 (Blue Carbon, Addamo et al. 2024). This prior modelling produced a map of predicted organic carbon concentrations in sediments throughout the study area. In this report we compare this map of modelled OC levels (based on environmental predictors) in marine sediments (top 10 cm) and the modelled EMODnet seabed habitat map for Europe (EUSeaMap) (version 2023). Thus, we can visualise the spatial relationship between organic carbon stores and seabed habitats. This spatial information could be used in Marine Spatial Planning, for example by indicating where seabed disturbance should be minimised to avoid release of carbon dioxide and other greenhouse gases from the seabed into the water column.

Introduction

European and international initiatives, such as [Biodiversity Strategy for 2030](#) (BDS, COM/2020/380 final) and [Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework](#) (GBF, CBD/COP/15/L25) adopted by the European Union and the Conference of Parties COP15 respectively, called for the protection of at least 30% of each marine habitat globally and at least 30% of all the ocean for worldwide effective marine biodiversity conservation by 2030. The Biodiversity Strategy also requests an additional commitment to strictly protect at least 10% of European seas. To support Marine Spatial Planning in European seas, the MPA Europe project will identify the optimal places to protect marine biodiversity and blue carbon stores in an ecologically representative network. The benefits of effective MPAs include not only the protection of biodiversity, but also the restoration of ecosystems and fisheries, generating benefits for fisheries and ecotourism, and enhancing ecosystem resilience to climate change (Costello, 2024).

The [Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change](#) (IPCC) has defined Blue Carbon as “all biologically driven carbon fluxes and storage in marine systems that are amenable to management”. So far, the Blue Carbon concept has mainly referred to marine sediment organic carbon (OC) that is captured and stored in sediments underlying seagrass meadows, tidal marshes, and mangrove forests. These plants dominated sediment habitats not only sequester aerial carbon dioxide through photosynthesis but also can accumulate organic matter rich sediments from land runoff and tidal inundation. Thus, they have a high capacity for OC storage and can all be managed through protection and restoration of lost ecosystems. Protection of their OC stocks may help reduce the risk that the carbon is degraded and released as CO₂ while restoration of lost habitats may increase OC storage and, thereby, contribute to mitigation of climate change. Such management also supports biodiversity, coastal protection, nutrient retention, and other key ecological functions and services (Nellemann et al., 2009; Duarte et al. 2013; Howard et al. 2014; Hilmi et al., 2021). However, in addition, finer grain sediments also accumulate organic carbon as our analysis of the organic carbon data has shown (Addamo et al., 2024). Protecting this seafloor Blue Carbon from disturbances that may release the stored carbon back into the water and atmosphere will help reduce greenhouse gas emissions (Howard et al.; 2023, Epstein et al., 2022). Efficient protection requires knowledge on the variability in sediment OC levels, and the factors controlling these.

Methods

We used the map of the modelled organic carbon previously developed by the MPA Europe project using boosted regression trees (BRT) (Addamo et al., 2024; Graversen et al., 2024; Lønborg et al., 2024). The model included different environmental factors, topographic rugosity as well as geomorphic features (Bio-Oracle v3.0, Assis et al., 2024) that might drive the OC levels of marine sediments (Addamo et al., 2024). The model was also validated based on environmental data associated with the over 32,000 OC samples (Graversen et al., 2023ab; Addamo et al., 2024).

We applied an organic carbon index (OCI) to the final raster layer with a spatial resolution of 0.05 degrees (ca 5 km). The provisional five-level OCI scoring system developed in Deliverable 4.4 (Graversen et al., 2024) was translated into a simpler 3-level score for ease of visualization on maps where: 1-low = 0-0.5%OC; 2-intermediate = 0.5-2 %OC; and 3-high = >0.5 %OC) (Addamo et al., 2024).

Since EMODnet seabed substrata data are not available for all the MPA Europe study area, they could not be incorporated in the model. However, the EMODnet broad-scale seabed habitat map for Europe (EUSeaMap) (version 2023) is here overlaid with the scored modelled map of OC to the

identify priority areas that should be considered for protection. The raster files of EUSeaMap are available here: https://github.com/iobis/mpaeu_sdm/tree/main/analysis/euseamap_2025. The spatial data visualization was done using QGIS v3.42 (2025).

Results

The areas with highest and high organic carbon concentrations ($> 0.5\%$ and $0.5\text{--}2\%$ OC) cover *ca* 0.2% and 8.5% of the study area respectively (Figure 1, A1). They include most coastal areas and some off-shore sites (e.g., White Sea, off Norway). The remaining $\sim 90\%$ of the area includes areas with no habitat data (Figure 2) and areas with $< 0.5\%$ OC. Although the Mediterranean has generally finer grain sediments than the Atlantic shelf it does not have as much area of high %OC as the Baltic and Black Seas (Figure 3). The rocky and other hard substrata, and biogenic habitats (that includes kelp, other seaweed, mussels, maerl etc.) occupy such a small area they are not visible on the maps (Figure 2, A2, A3).

Discussion

The purpose of this exploratory test was mainly to identify how the organic carbon data aligned spatially with the high-level classification of marine habitats. We found that coastal biogenic habitats, some of which are important as carbon stores (e.g., seagrass) and some as carbon sequestration but not storage (e.g., kelp and seaweeds mostly on rocky substrata), occupy a relatively small proportion of European seas. The former are important for both carbon sequestration and storage, and as habitats for other species, particularly *Posidonia* meadows in the Mediterranean. However, significant offshore areas also accumulate organic carbon in fine muddy sediments. Because these habitats are sheltered from wave and current exposure, the fauna are vulnerable to disturbance. Thus, bottom trawling or dredging is likely to have significant impacts on the benthic fauna as well as risk releasing greenhouse gases from the seabed. Finally, highly content areas and vulnerable habitats should be highly prioritised for protection) and would include coastal areas (e.g. Scandinavian and Mediterranean coasts), as well as offshore sites (e.g., Baltic, Black Sea and off Canary Island in the Atlantic Ocean).

Our future analysis will include a more comprehensive dataset on sediment OC from the updated EURO-CARBON database with over 60,000 data records (Lønborg, 2025), the new improved modelling of OC content in marine sediment (Lønborg, in prep), as well as a more detailed and quantitative comparative analyses with each EMODnet broad-scale seabed substratum and habitat. These results will be compared with the maps of human activities from EMODnet and other sources (e.g., fishery seabed trawling) indicating the risk such activity poses to organic carbon storage capacity. Finally, a comparison with the Natura 2000 sites, and classification of MPA in a recent analysis, will indicate how well protected the areas high in organic carbon are.

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Table 1. List of seabed substrata (EUSeaMap 2023) included in Figure 2. Note that the biogenic (blue) and rock (purple) habitats occupy such a small area they are not visible in the map.

Colour code	Substratum
Blue	Biogenic substrate
	Bivalve reefs
	Coralligenous platforms
	<i>Limaria hians</i> beds
	Dead mattes of <i>Posidonia oceanica</i>
	<i>Desmophyllum pertusum</i> (former <i>Lophelia pertusa</i>)
	Facies with <i>Ficopomatus enigmaticus</i> of the euryhaline and/or eurythermal lagoon biocenosis
	<i>Modiolus modiolus</i> beds
	Mussel beds
	<i>Mytilus edulis</i> beds
	<i>Ostrea edulis</i> beds
	<i>Posidonia oceanica</i> “barrier reefs”
	<i>Posidonia oceanica</i> meadows
	<i>Sabellaria alveolata</i> reefs
	<i>Sabellaria spinulosa</i> reefs
	<i>Serpula vermicularis</i> reefs
Worms’ reefs	
Light Green	Coarse & mixed sediment
	Coarse substratum
	Mixed sediment
Yellow	Fine mud
	Fine mud or Sandy mud or Muddy sand
	Muddy sand
Red	Sand
	Sandy mud
	Sandy mud or Muddy sand
Purple	Rock or other hard substrata
Grey	Seabed
	Sediment

Figure 1. Map of modelled sediment organic carbon (OC) in the MPA Europe study area. It represents OC level 2 and 3 (yellow and red areas, respectively). No coastline is included in the figure but it is visible because there are high OC concentrations close to the coast, especially where there are deep inlets and fjords, e.g. close-up area along Scottish coast (blue box at the bottom). Due to the resolution of the figure, the small yellow areas are perceived as black. For detailed map on individual OC level see Appendices Figures A1 and A2.

Figure 2. Map of modelled EMODnet seabed substrata habitat map for Europe (EUSeaMap 2023) available in the MPA Europe study area. Yellow = fine mud, sandy mud or muddy sand. Red = sand, sandy mud, or muddy sand. Green = coarse and mixed sediment. Purple = rock or other hard substrata. Blue = biogenic habitats, e.g. close-up area along the southern Italian coast (black box at the bottom). Grey = unknown substratum. For detailed information on individual substratum and habitat see Table 1 and Figures A3-A8. Source EMODnet Seabed Habitats (right) (last access: April 2025).

Figure 3. Map of modelled fine mud, sandy mud and muddy (upper map), sand and muddy sand (middle map), and coarse sand and mixed sediment (lower map) from EUSeaMap (2023) in the MPA Europe study area. Note the generally finer sediments in the Mediterranean than the Atlantic shelf.

Appendices

Figure A1. Map of modelled sediment organic carbon (OC) in the MPA Europe study area. It only represents OC level 2 (yellow areas, upper map) and level 3 (red areas, lower map). Otherwise as in Figure 1.

Figure A2. Map of modelled rock and other hard substrata (EUSeaMap 2023) available in the MPA Europe study area. Due to the resolution of the figure, the small purple areas are perceived as black, e.g. close-up area along Norwegian coast (blue box at the bottom).

Figure A3. Map of modelled biogenic habitats (EUSeaMap 2023) available in the MPA Europe study area. Due to the resolution of the figure, the small blue areas are perceived as black, e.g. close-up area along western Mediterranean coast (blue box at the bottom). For more information about the list of biogenic habitats included, see Table 1.

